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Prostate cancer cured in a week by machine without side effects

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We had two patients with prostate cancer at the Vitamed Clinic in Aleksandrów Łódzki.

First patient Mr S, age 65, had a problem with urinary incontinence in the night and also problem with urination, he felt burning. This patient didn't take chemo and radiation. We started with the first treatment on 24th of June 2019 on Monday. The second treatment was on Wednesday on 26th of June. He declared that he felt the difference. He said that he didn't feel burning when urinating. Third treatment was on Friday 28th of June. Patient said that his night urinary incontinence stopped. He felt good. After third treatment after two weeks patient decided to do blood test and ultrasonography. Blood tests confirmed that he is cured and on ultrasonography he observed that the tumour is getting smaller. At the end of August, the patient repeated tests, blood and ultrasonography. The tests said clearly that he is cured, and ultrasonography confirmed that the tumour is much smaller.

The second patient Mr A, age 68, had prostate cancer but he had no accompanying symptoms. He learned about the disease only

two weeks before undergoing Cellsonic therapy. He did not take any chemo or radiation. He had big fears to decide on this therapy but after consulting he decided. His treatment was at exactly the same time as the previous patient. He felt nothing during the therapy and did not believe in its success. But the tests confirmed the success, he was cured. And as with the previous patient, Mr A repeated the tests at the end of August. Ultrasound showed that the tumour was much smaller and the blood test clearly stated that the patient was cured.

This is a great breakthrough and success that we can cure patients in such a short time. We are waiting for further applications, patients are very cautious about this therapy, inexperienced doctors who prefer to treat this disease with old methods are giving us bad reviews.

We don't give up, to educate doctors, present the Cellsonic machine and show that prostate cancer can be cured in one week.